

On the relations of Fibonacci to the determinants of the sum of the Fibonacci-Hessenberg matrices

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ABSTRACT

The Fibonacci sequence is defined by $f_0 = 0, f_1 = 1$ and $f_n = f_{n-1} + f_{n-2}; n \geq 2$. An $n \times n$ matrix A is called a (lower) Hessenberg matrix if all entries above the superdiagonal are zero. A Fibonacci-Hessenberg matrices are matrices whose determinants are in the form $tf_{n-1} + f_{n-2}$ or $fn_{-1} + fn_{-2}$ for some real or complex number t . Define $n \times n$ and an $n \times n$ matrix $\mathcal{E}_{n,t}$, a new matrix is formed by adding one row of weight one and starting with alternating 1's and 0's, starting a 1, to the left of the obtained matrix. Let i denote the usual complex unit with $i^2 = -1$. Replacing the entry of $\mathcal{E}_{n,t}$ located in the i^{th} row $(i+1)^{th}$ column, $1 \leq i \leq n$, with $(-1)^{i+n} i$, we obtain another Hessenberg matrix denoted $H_{n,t}$. In this paper, we take the sum of $\mathcal{E}_{n,t}$ and $H_{n,t}$ and show that the determinants of the sum of the two hessenberg matrices are not equal to the sum of the determinants of the two hessenberg matrices. We also provide illustrations and fibonacci relations of the determinants of the resulted sum.

Keywords: *Fibonacci sequence, Hessenberg matrices, Fibonacci-Hessenberg matrices, determinants*

I. INTRODUCTION

This study provides expositions and extensions of the works of Esmaeli (2006) where the author defined the Fibonacci sequence as $f_0 = 0, f_1 = 1$ and

$f_{n-1} + f_{n-2}, n \geq 2$. Given a matrix $A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{pmatrix}$, we

define the determinant of A , (also denoted by $\det A$ to be scalar $\det A = a_{11}a_{22} - a_{12}a_{21}$.

An $n \times n$ matrix A is called a (lower) Hessenberg matrix if all entries above the superdiagonal are zero. Setting $A_1 = (1)$ and defined A as:

$$A_n := \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 1 & 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 \\ 1 & 2 & 1 & & & \\ & & & & & \\ & & & & 0 & \\ & & & & 2 & 1 \\ 1 & & & & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}_{n \times n}$$

In Esmaeli (2006) states that Fibonacci-Hessenberg matrices are matrices whose determinants are in the form $tf_{n-1} + f_{n-2}$ or $f_{n-1} + tf_{n-2}$ for some real complex number t . Define $\mathcal{E}_{1,t} = (t+1)$ and an $n \times n$ matrix $\mathcal{E}_{n,t}$, a

new matrix is formed by adding one row of weight one and starting with 1 to the top of $\varepsilon_{n,t}$ and then adding a new column with alternating 1's and 0's, starting a 1; to the left of the obtained matrix.

Example 1.1 $\varepsilon_{5,t} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & t+1 \end{pmatrix}$

Let i denote the usual complex unit with $i^2 = -1$. Replacing the entry of $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ located in the i^{th} row and the $(i+1)^{th}$ column, $1 \leq i < n$, with $(-1)^{i+n}i$; we obtain another Hessenberg matrix denoted by $H_{n,t}$.

Example 1.2. $H_{n,t} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & i & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -i & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & i & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & -i \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & t+1 \end{pmatrix}$

To show the result of this paper; we introduced the following results:

Remark 1.1. According to Ching (1993) The $\varepsilon_{n,0}, n \geq 1$, is fn .

Proposition 1.1. The determinants of $\varepsilon_{n,t}$ and $H_{n,t}$, denoted by $e_{n,t}$ and $h_{n,t}$, respectively, are $e_{1,t} = h_{n,t} = t+1$ and $e_{n,t} = h_{n,t} = tf_{n-1} + f_n$ for $n \geq 2$. Thus $\varepsilon_{n,t}$ and $H_{n,t}$ are Fibonacci-Hessenberg matrices.

2. Main Result: The Sum of Two Hessenberg Matrices

Let $A = [a_{ij}]$ and $B = [b_{ij}]$ be of the same size. Then the sum matrices A and B , denoted by $A + B$ is obtained by adding the corresponding elements of

A and B ; that is

$$A + B = [a_{ij}] + [b_{ij}] = [a_{ij} + b_{ij}]$$

Definition 2.1. version 1: Define

$$M_{n,t} = \varepsilon_{n,t} + H_{n,t}$$

s.t.,

$$M_{n,t} = \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 1+i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2 & i-1 & 0 \\ 2 & 0 & 2 & \\ \\ 2 & 0 & 0 & 2t+2 \end{pmatrix}$$

Definition 2.1 show that the $M_{n,t}$ is formed by replacing the $\varepsilon_{n,t}$ located in the i^{th} row and $(i+1)^{th}$ column, $1 \leq i < n$, with $1 + (-1)^{i+n}i$, and replacing the 1 by 2.

Define $\varepsilon_{1,t} = (t+1)$ and an $n \times n$ matrix $\varepsilon_{n,t}$, a new matrix is formed by adding one row of weight one and starting with 1 to the top of $\varepsilon_{n,t}$ and then adding a new column with alternating 1's and 0's, starting a 1; to the left of the obtained matrix.

Theorem 2.1. The determinants of $M_{n,t}$, denoted by $m_{n,t}$ is

$$m_{n,t} = 2^n(t+1) \forall n \geq 1$$

Proof. Note that Thus, the statement is true for $n = 1$.

Suppose that the formula holds for n , that is $m_{n,t} = 2^n(t+1) \forall n \geq 1$. By Definition 2.1, and consider $M_{n,t}$ be the matrix obtained from $M_{n,t}$ by means of deleting the first row and second column. It easy to see that using the co-factor expansion along the first row on both $M_{n,t}$ and $M_{n,t}$ results in $m_{n,t} = 2^n(t+1)$. Therefore, the results follows.

Remark 2.1. *The determinants of the sum of $\varepsilon_{n,t}$ and $H_{n,t}$ are not equal to the sum of the determinants of $\varepsilon_{n,t}$ and $H_{n,t}$.*

To see this, note that Proposition 1.1 shows that $e_{n,t} = h_{n,t} = tf_{n-1} + f_n$ for $n \geq 2$ and from Theorem 2.1 $m_{n,t} = 2^n(t+1)$ in which $m_{n,t}$ is the determinants of $M_{n,t}$, where $M_{n,t} = \varepsilon_{n,t} + H_{n,t}$

Remark 2.2. $m_{n,t} \geq c_{n,t} + h_{n,t}, \forall$ positive t

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